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1. Executive summary

This fourth deliverable of WP6 aims to contribute to the dissemination of project results related to promising strategies of using tree/shrub leaves for livestock feeding. This includes the development of appropriate communication and application tools. Results from various tasks were regularly shared with farmers through innovation platforms (IPs) and dissemination days, mainly organised by WP2, as well as workshops by WP6. These meetings allowed the WP6 teams in the three intervention countries to convey key messages with practical, site-specific recommendations on why and how to include woody fodder in animal feed rations in each participating country. Stakeholder reactions were documented, followed by discussions, joint conclusions and identification of key messages for further dissemination via leaflets and other classical materials that can easily be distributed. Necessary subsequent steps were also planned or decided during these meetings.

This deliverable also includes the summary of scientific articles, reports, and students' theses realised within the project, as well as the publication of updates on the project's website. These outreach materials rather target the scientific and R&D community in order to stimulate discussion and create synergies across different projects and regions.

2. Activities with the producers

Numerous activities that directly involved livestock keepers were carried out in all participating countries and are described in more detail below by country and year.

2.0 Dissemination of manuring and mulching strategies in Mali and Burkina Faso

The tested manuring/mulching strategies were a transversal topic disseminated during SustainSahel WP6 dissemination days and IP meetings from 2022 to 2024 in Mali and Burkina Faso. Focus groups, practical training (Fig. 1), and guided visits to our manuring field experiment in Mafèya were used to disseminate relevant practices of mulching fields with tree/shrub leafy biomass, as well as applying manure derived from leaf-fed animals. The activities included:

- Four (n=4) focus group meetings with relay producers in 2022 were organized in Mali (n=3) and Burkina Faso (n=1)
- Three (n=3) practical training days were organized in Mali (n=2) and Burkina Faso (n=1) in 2023
- Two (n=2) guided farmer visits were organized to demonstrate the mulching effect of tree/shrub leaves and the manuring effect of leaf-derived animal excreta on sorghum yield in Mafèya, Mali

Figure 1: Siriki Fané from WP6 (right) discussing leaf mulch application with stakeholders in Mali

2.0.1 Group meetings with relay producers in Mali and Burkina Faso

In 2022, feedback sessions were held in Mali in the following project communities; Mafèya (5th February; Fig. 2A), Doumba (8th February), and Tiètiguila (15th February; Fig. 2B). For Burkina Faso the same sessions were organized in Saria (15th May; Fig. 3) and Ramokodogo (16th May; Fig. 4). These sessions aimed at discussing interview results with farmers after having collected, with their consent, socioeconomic and farm management information during February to May 2021. Farmers were informed (i) why it is important to integrate trees, particularly *Vitellaria paradoxa* and *Parkia biglobosa*, in their crop fields, (ii) how to manage these trees to maximize tree-crop complementarity, and (iii) how to break tree seed dormancy and raise seedlings. The latter aspect was intensified through hands-on training.

Figure 2. Feedback sessions with farmers in Mafèya (A) and Tiètiguila (B)

Figure 3: Meeting with lead farmers in Saria (left) and Ramonkodogo (right), Burkina Faso

2.0.2 Organization of farmer field schools and field visits in Mali

The first farmer school was organized for farmers in Mafèya (26 June 2023; Fig. 4) at the beginning of the rainy season, for them to learn how to apply animal manure and leafy tree biomass to cropland; our experimental site was used for this training purpose. Due to farmers' interest in applying animal manure and leafy biomass on their own farms, we asked them to elect a leader who we would visit on the own farm and train as lead farmers. The lead farmers in Mafèya and Doumba (Fig. 5) were thus visited for this purpose on 20 and 21 July 2023, respectively.

Figure 4. Field school session in Mali on manuring/mulching by WP6, in collaboration with WP4

Figure 5. Application of fresh and dry leafy tree biomass and animal manure by the lead farmer in Doumba, Mali

The second farmer field school was organized in October 2023, at the end of the rainy season, for the farmers to observe and evaluate the effect of leafy tree biomass and animal manure application on the grain and biomass yield of sorghum (Fig. 6). Farmers observed that sorghum yield was higher in plots fertilized with the leaves of *Ficus sycomorus* than on un-amended plots. Although the farmers were enthusiastic about adopting the green leafy tree biomass mulching practice, they were concerned about the high labour requirements and substantial quantity of leafy biomass required. It was recommended that farmers should engage in boundary planting of shrubs and improve tree fallows to address these challenges. Additionally, farmers were informed about which type of leafy tree biomass decomposes faster than others to guide them in their selection of leaf mulch material.

Figure 6. Mulching a sorghum with leaf biomass at the beginning of rainy season (left) and results of the manuring experiment demonstrated to farmers at the end of rainy season (right) in Mafèya, Mali

2.1 Burkina Faso

The WP6 team participated in approximately ten meetings with producers held between 2022 and 2024; these were focusing on disseminating innovations in the use of woody fodder for animal feeding and health care. These meetings included:

- Two meetings with relay producers in 2022 at the two sites Saria and Yilou
- Two dissemination days and IP meetings each at the two sites in 2023
- Two meetings organised by the WP6 team in 2024 to provide feedback on the results of tested rations / treatments and discuss challenges and opportunities for using woody fodder
- Two additional IP meetings in 2024 (Saria and Yilou)

2.1.1 Training sessions with producers in 2022

In 2022, training sessions were held for relay producers and site facilitators on technologies validated by the project team in Burkina Faso. WP6 members presented:

- Methods for conserving woody fodder and supplementing small ruminants with tree/shrub leaves
- Sheep fattening with a ration including woody fodder
- Challenges in animal feeding
- Alternative solutions to feeding challenges, including the use of woody fodder
- Best practices for fattening ruminant livestock

At each meeting, after these presentations, participants ranked the introduced technologies based on their importance. Overall, sheep fattening on rations including woody fodder ranked third, after using improved seeds and Zai (planting pits) for cereal cropping. The main factors influencing this ranking included their economic needs, the quest for food security, necessary social expenditure (such as for schooling and healthcare), and the manure requirements of food crops.

2.1.2 IP meeting and dissemination days in 2023 in Yilou and Saria

In 2023, the WP6 team participated in IP meetings and dissemination days. The meetings, held on 8 May in Yilou and 11 May in Saria, aimed to develop action plans for 2023. The primary challenges related to

integrating crops, shrubs, and livestock were identified, followed by proposed actions to address these difficulties. Table I summarises the major challenges and proposed actions for WP6.

Table I Major challenges and possible solutions identified during the meetings in Yilou and Saria

	Challenge	Solution
Yilou	Lack of vaccination parks for livestock	
	Recurrent poultry and small ruminant diseases (diarrhoea)	Raising awareness among livestock farmers about animal vaccination Building farmers' capacity to prevent diseases in poultry and small ruminants
Saria	High animal mortality at the start of the winter period (cool dry season)	Finding practicable and sustainable solutions for feeding and watering animals during the dry season (hunger and thirst are causes of animal mortality) Identifying other causes of animal mortality and finding adequate solutions. Raising awareness about the use of herbicides, which contribute to animal mortality
	Insufficient water: watering points drying up (up to 20 km walks needed to water livestock)	
	High prices for animal feed	Complement poor rations with woody fodder
	Difficulties in treating certain animal diseases (due to the high number of animals required for the use of certain bottled products) Know the correct moment for vaccination	Advocacy to review the packaging of certain products to reduce the number of animals treated per bottle Recommendation for animal owners to create a list of those needing vaccination to share bottles among smallholders Advice on the best time to vaccinate, e.g., reminders via a calendar
	Producers' mistrust of the treatment of animals by animal resource officers (cases of animal mortality reported after the treatment by vets)	Investigating the issue to better understand it Checking the effectiveness of products used following investigations Further enhancing the skills of vets in diagnosing and treating animal diseases Plea to increase the number of vets per municipality for more preventive diagnosis of animal diseases

At the first dissemination days held in May 2023, all PhD students of SustainSahel in Burkina Faso presented the activities they had carried out and the results achieved to date.

For WP6, the presentation by doctoral student Linda Gabriella Traoré focused on:

- (i) Palatability tests with ligneous forage plants with sheep;
- (ii) Tannin content of certain ligneous plants;
- (iii) Tests on the prevalence and load of gastrointestinal (GI) parasites in small ruminants, and
- (iv) Linda also explained the use of the FAMACHA® card to identify GI-infested animals during the rainy season.

Based on the palatability test results that help detect the most palatable woody fodder species, she recommended that farmers collect, dry, and store the leaves of these species to feed their animals during the long dry season.

Regarding the infestation of small ruminants with gastrointestinal parasites, it appears that animals are most affected during the rainy season, with young animals and goats being the most vulnerable ones. It was therefore recommended that infested animals be detected as early as possible using the FAMACHA® method and treated with products prescribed by a veterinary officer.

The trial on the use of woody fodder to combat gastrointestinal parasites revealed that trees and shrubs, given their richness in certain metabolites such as tannins, could act effectively against gastrointestinal parasites. *Ziziphus mauritiana*, *Lannea microcarpa*, *Ficus sycomorus*, and *Azadirachta indica* were found to have high tannin contents. Additional on-farm tests are currently executed and evaluated (summer/autumn 2024) to further explore the first insights gained in 2023.

During discussions in Yilou, producers raised the following concerns or wishes:

- More support for producers in the production of *Faidherbia albida* and *Ziziphus mauritiana* as animal feed;
- More information on the FAMACHA® method;
- Adequate availability of animal health workers to support producers on animal health issues;
- Sharing of information on the treatment of the "Gomboro" disease with neem (*Azadirachta indica*) leaves by livestock producers;
- Sharing information on upcoming sheep fattening tests with tree foliage. Producers were informed of the conditions for participation, and a list of interested producers was compiled.

During discussions in Saria, the following concerns were raised:

- The challenges of conducting on-farm tests with feeding leaves as natural anthelmintics, because some producers reported that consumption of *Lannea microcarpa* causes diarrhoea in animals;
- Concerns that consuming the leaves of *Bombax costatum* (Kapok tree) could cause abortion in pregnant animals;
- The perception that eating peanut hulls can cause diarrhoea in animals.

The WP6 team members shared their knowledge on these issues and, where own experience was lacking, promised to come back to producers with well-founded information.

The theme of the next IP meeting, held in October 2023, was "Recurrent and high mortality of small ruminants due to diarrhoea and bloat during the rainy season". This topic was covered by WP6, and the presentations focused on:

- i) Understanding and managing the problem from the producers' perspective;
- ii) Understanding the causes and current solutions from the perspective of the technical livestock services;
- iii) Information on the effectiveness of certain woody species in combating parasites by WP6 members.

In WP6, a study on the anthelmintic effectiveness of certain ligneous plants against internal parasites was carried out in Saria in 2023 and was repeated in 2024; preliminary results have been shared at Tropentag 2023 in Berlin (see chapter 3.3) the results are currently being analysed.

Recommendations for producers included having animals vaccinated during the annual vaccination campaigns organised by the government with the support of IP members and relay producers in their villages, and contacting veterinary agents wherever possible to diagnose and treat sick animals.

Recommendations for research (INERA and/or UNB) were to share the results of the study on the anthelmintic effectiveness of some ligneous plants against internal parasites carried out at Saria with members of the IPs and relay producers in Yilou. They were also asked to conduct experiments with other products used by farmers that are not currently the subject of WVP6 research, such as the use of edible oil to combat poisoning, the use of sugar and edible oil to address plastic bag ingestion, the use of *Piliostigma* pods (*Piliostigma reticulatum*; Mooré name: Bāgende) and the bark of the caïlcédrat (*Khaya senegalensis*; Mooré name: Kouka) for deworming animals, and the use of yeast and water from fermented sorrel grains (*Hibiscus sabdariffa*) to combat bloating in animals.

2.1.3 WP 6 meetings 2024 for feedback and discussion

In 2024, WVP6 organised a feedback meeting with producers on the results of its research and dissemination activities, and engaged in discussions with producers on the opportunities, risks and challenges of feeding animals with the leaves of trees and shrubs. At the Yilou site, training of farmers in sheep fattening was provided to compensate for the lack of fattening tests conducted at this location. A video on the use of the FAMACHA® card was also shown. These meetings resulted in the following feedback from stakeholders:

- Several producers who participated in the activities expressed their satisfaction and were pleasantly surprised to see that the animals ate the harvested and dried woody leaves well and gained more weight than the animals fed according to traditional practice;
- The producers unanimously agreed on the advantages of feeding (dried) woody fodder for increasing weight gain in sheep, such as *Faidherbia albida* pods and *Piliostigma reticulatum* pods, which many of them are using;
- They also recognised the effectiveness of feeding leaves of *Khaya senegalensis* against internal parasites;
- Additionally, they reported that organic manure from animals fed on woody fodder (*Khaya senegalensis*, *Pterocarpus lucens*, and *Anogeissus leiocarpus*) resulted in higher cereal yields compared to the yield obtained with other types of organic manure;
- However, the scarcity of certain species, such as *Pterocarpus lucem*, *Ficus sycomorus* and *Khaya senegalensis* was highlighted and the wish was expressed that (seedlings of) these species could be made available in the respective villages;
- A major challenge identified was the reckless cutting of (branches of) adult trees, with pressure on trees varying from village to village.

The following suggestions were made by the participants to facilitate access to and availability of woody fodder plants:

- Establish nurseries with the desired species: *Ficus sycomorus*, *Khaya senegalensis*, *Pterocarpus lucens*, *Pterocarpus erinaceus*, *Faidherbia albida* and *Ziziphus mauritiana*;
- Provide producers with seedlings of woody fodder species according to local needs. The research team committed to providing the seedlings, while producers committed to maintaining them in their fields;
- Popularise a sickle-shaped tool with a long wooden handle, which can be used to gently collect leaves without climbing the trees;
- Encourage that leaves of woody fodder plants be collected, dried (in the shade), stored in bags, and kept out of sun and rain to preserve the nutritional qualities of the leaves;
- Use cereal storage bins, often used to store groundnut tops, for storage of collected tree/shrub leaves, as suggested by an agropastoralist from the IP.

In conclusion, the majority of producers expressed satisfaction and indicated that they had learned a great deal from the activities carried out. They are committed to putting the knowledge they have gained into practice.

Further steps resulting from the suggestions include:

- Establish nurseries and promote planting of popular species: *Pterocarpus erinaceus*, *P. lucens*, and *Ficus sycomorus*;
- Commitment by producers to care well for the plants if seedlings are provided by INERA;
- Foster cooperation with the environmental officer in each locality, who can offer advice on how to collect the woody fodder leaves;
- Draw on support from the farmers' organisation (Confederation Paysanne du Faso) to enhance collaboration with producers;
- Promote the planting and maintenance of woody seedlings that have naturally sprouted in the fields.

Following these meetings, the WP6 team submitted a request for seedlings to the WP4 collaborators, who acquired and made available 170 seedlings in Yilou and 144 in Saria from six species (*Faidherbia albida*, *Khaya senegalensis*, *Bombax costatum*, *Pterocarpus erinaceus*, *Ziziphus mauritiana*, *Adansonia digitata*), which were planted. Picture 1 shows a producer in Yilou with her received plants of *Adansonia digitata*.

Picture 1 Grower who received plants of *Adansonia digitata*

2.1.4 Additional IP meetings 2024

The 2024 IP workshop was held on July 2 in Saria and on July 5 in Yilou. The topic was "Exchange on co-culture techniques of crops, shrubs and trees tested during the past project implementation period and discussion on the life of the platform". WP6 contributed by presenting a dissemination poster on the collection and conservation of woody fodder leaves. The poster was also reproduced as a leaflet in A4 format and distributed to members of the IP.

At the end of the presentation, the producers appreciated the content of the poster, finding it very useful and easy to understand. They expressed their willingness to apply the technique but raised concerns about the availability and accessibility of the woody fodder species they preferred, as well as the forestry services'

ban on cutting trees. Therefore, planting more desirable fodder trees and shrubs to increase their availability was deemed essential. Figure 2 shows two advanced versions of the poster.

Sustain Sahel

Technique de collecte et conservation des feuilles d'arbres et arbustes fourragers

Le stockage de feuilles d'arbres et arbustes est une technique qui permet de disposer des fourrages ligneux en saison sèche. La technique consiste à collecter les feuilles des arbres/arbustes appâtés par les ruminants en période de pleine feuillaison, les sécher et les stocker pour l'utilisation en période de soudure.

- Émonner soigneusement des branches 20-30% du houppier
- Transporter vers le lieu de séchage / stockage
- Pré-tendre au soleil à l'abri des animaux durant une journée
- Poursuivre le séchage à l'ombre à l'abri des animaux et retourner une fois par jour pendant 3 à 4 jours
- Stocker dans des sacs à l'abri de l'eau et du soleil
- Nourrir les animaux en arrosoir ou pendant la saison sèche

Les avantages:
 Diversification la ressource alimentaire en saison sèche;
 Disponibilité d'un stock d'aliment de qualité;
 Limiter la pression sur les arbres et arbustes en saison sèche chaude.

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Prélever soigneusement des branches 20-30% du houppier

Transporter vers le lieu de séchage / stockage

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Les avantages:
 Diversification la ressource alimentaire en saison sèche;
 Disponibilité d'un stock d'aliment de qualité;
 Limiter la pression sur les arbres et arbustes en saison sèche chaude.

Picture 2 Two updated versions of the poster on the collection and conservation of woody fodder leaves

The discussions with producers helped to identify the key messages to be disseminated concerning a) fattening operations and b) health care:

- a.1) The woody plants most preferred by sheep in Saria are: *Bombax costatum*, *Ficus sycomorus*, *Khaya senegalensis*, *Pterocarpus erinaceus*, and *Ziziphus mauritiana*;
- a.2) Including leaves of woody fodder plants in the diet increases the weight gain of fattening sheep;
- a.3) Rations including 40% of *Ficus sycomorus* leaves, *Khaya senegalensis* leaves and *Piliostigma reticulatum* pods yield good growth performance;
- a.4) Sheep fed on *Ficus sycomorus*, *Pterocarpus erinaceus* and *Khaya senegalensis* foliage showed similar weight gains to those fed on groundnut tops;
- a.5) Mastering fattening techniques (choosing the right ram, mixing the right ingredients, providing housing and prophylaxis against diseases, and maintaining management records) makes the fattening activity more profitable.
- b.1) The rainy season, particularly August, is the period when sheep and goats are heavily infested with gastrointestinal nematodes;
- b.2) Small ruminants, especially goats, need to be treated effectively during this period.
- b.3) *Khaya senegalensis* leaves (50% of the ration) are effective against gastrointestinal nematodes (strongyles) after 7 days of feeding, reducing the faecal egg count by 42%;

- b.4) An alternative would be to feed small ruminants with leaves of woody plants such as *Ziziphus mauritiana* and *Ficus sycomorus*.

Further impressions of the meetings held in Burkina Faso are shown in Pictures 3-5.

Picture 3 Presenting results of a feeding trial

Picture 4 Discussion with farmers

Picture 5 Discussion with farmers

2.2 Mali

The WP6 team in Mali participated in nine meetings with producers, including six dissemination days, either in the farmers' villages or at the IPR station, one IP meeting, and a workshop organised to share the results of WP6.

- Three meetings in 2022 took place during farmers' days in Mafèya (11 June 2022) and Tiètiguila (24 October 2022), as well as during the “station day” at IPR/IFRA in Katibougou (19 October 2022).
- Five meetings in 2023 included a farmers' day in Doumba Banani (15 May 2023), a farmers' day at the IPR/IFRA Higher Education Centre in Katibougou (29 May 2023), an IP meeting in Koulikoro (30 May 2023), and a farmers' day at the IPR/IFRA premises in November 2023.
- One meeting in 2024 was organised by the team in Katibougou as a workshop to share the results of WP6 activities on 4 May 2024.

2.2.1 Farmers' days 2022 in Mafèya, Tiètiguila, Katibougou

At the Mafèya site, the farmers' days provided an opportunity to visit agro-forestry trial plots in the farming environment, with explanations of the objectives and preliminary results from the 2021/2022 cropping season, as well as a discussion of forecast for the 2022/2023 season. During the meeting, the WP6 team disseminated the following key messages:

- Leaves and fruits (though fruit trees were not specifically studied in this project, they were identified as useful in other projects) of locally growing woody plants are a rich source of feed during the dry season when grasses are scarce and of low nutritional value;
- Animals that are well-fed on tree leaves are less susceptible to diseases;
- Leaves of local and exotic woody fodder species, when dried and well-preserved during times of abundance, can make a considerable contribution to animal nutrition during lean periods.

Producers embraced the innovation of collecting the leaves of woody trees during periods of abundance, drying them in the shade, and storing them for use during feed shortages. The participants agreed that useful multi-purpose trees growing in cereal fields should be preserved at an optimum density, to ensure that they do not negatively affect crop production.

At the Tiètiguila site, the relay farmers' plots were visited, followed by presentations of partial results and testimonials on the conducted activities. The WP6 team gave key messages relating to:

- i) The collection and conservation of crop residues, which make an important contribution to livestock feed in the lean season;
- ii) Local and exotic woody fodder species present in crop fields, which improve soil fertility (through leaf shedding and reducing wind erosion) and contribute to livestock feed.

Stakeholder reactions were as follows:

- The currently cultivated improved sorghum variety produces more seeds and high quality residues (stalks) for livestock feed;
- The integration of trees and crops is traditional practice, but with the experience of IPR technicians, we are now moving towards managing the number of trees per hectare;
- Trees provide us with fruits and fodder for our animals.

In conclusion, the field days allowed the WP6 team to observe farmers working together with knowledge and skills to improve soil quality and animal feed through trees. In-depth knowledge of the different species growing in farmers' fields and their management should be further explored.

The first on-station farmers' day at IPR/IFRA Katibougou involved a visit to station plots with intercropping of *Acacia albida*, cowpea and sorghum, and of plots where *Gliricidia sepium* is associated with sorghum and groundnut.

The key message delivered by the WP6 team was the important role of ligneous plants as livestock feed, particularly in the case of *Gliricidia sepium*, which is cultivated and praised by some producers collaborating with WP4 in Mafèya.

Participants were very interested in growing *Gliricidia sepium*, having realised that in addition to producing fodder, the species helps restore soil health (because it fixes nitrogen and produces substantial leaf litter) and can be propagated successfully by planting cuttings. Many participants cut branches to make their own cuttings for planting at home.

The day provided an opportunity to learn more about integrating livestock, crops and trees, and specifically about *Gliricidia sepium*. However, successful planting of trees remains a challenge, as producers reported frequent failures of seedling /cutting establishment due to termite attacks.

The next steps will involve training of collaborating producers, relay farmers and IP members in the production of *Gliricidia sepium* plants and intercropping with cereals, as well as supplying *Gliricidia sepium* seeds and seeds/seedlings of other woody fodder species.

2.2.2 Dissemination activities 2023 in Doumba Banani, Koulikoro and Katibougou

The farmer field day at Doumba Banani included a visit to demonstration plots showcasing the research activities carried out by IPR/IFRA. The WP6 team delivered key messages on the integration of crops, trees and livestock, and on the use of crop residues as livestock feed. This practice also allows for keeping animals in barns and storing their manure for later application to crop fields, while supplementing them with leaves from fodder trees offers a sustainable alternative for livestock development, particularly for small-scale farmers.

Following the WP6 presentation, collaborating farmers shared their experiences. The participants embraced the innovation of collecting leaves from woody plants during periods of abundance, drying them in the shade, and storing them for use during feed shortages. These contributions demonstrated that collaborating farmers have the knowledge and skills to feed animals with woody fodder and recognise the value of their manure for crop cultivation, highlighting the benefits of integrated agricultural production for the optimised use of resources and nutrient recycling.

During the farmers' day at the IPR/IFRA Higher Education Centre in Katibougou (Koulikoro), the focus was on presenting partial results of the research team and gathering testimonies from direct collaborators. The WP6 team discussed the collection and conservation of fodder resources, particularly tree foliage, which contributes to livestock feeding and reduces the need for expensive concentrated feed. The participants were pleased with the results and expressed interest in developing fodder resources, especially with a focus on tree leaves. They also requested that *Gliricidia sepium* seeds and seedlings be made available.

The participants acknowledged that the activities undertaken were addressing the socio-economic and production challenges faced by agro-pastoralists, as well as helping to mitigate environmental problems. The next step, as agreed by participants, would be to manage natural fodder species sustainably, a discussion that would need to involve local authorities.

At the meeting of the Innovation Platforms (IPs), an action plan for Koulikoro was drawn up, which included:

- Adoption of local regulations to define animal corridors and grazing areas during the rainy season;
- Organising village consultations to develop local agreements to protect fields from free-ranging animals;
- Training producers in woody fodder cultivation and conservation;
- Extend the planting of *Gliricidia sepium* across all villages;
- Training producers in each village to produce and maintain tree seedlings, facilitating easier access to these species; Enrichment of crop residues (with woody fodder) and improved techniques for feeding these residues to animals;
- Addressing water pollution caused by pesticides.

Stakeholders called for active involvement of each IP member to help achieve the set objectives and to make the IP more dynamic and sustainable. This meeting also helped to identify and prioritise the major challenges faced by producers within crop-tree-livestock systems. Establishing an IP and its action plan has made it easier to coordinate activities, enabling stakeholders to work together effectively without organisational difficulties. Ensuring the smooth functioning of the IPs is a priority for future actions.

The second farmers' day at the IPR/IFRA station included a visit to experimental plots and the presentation of partial results. The WP6 team shared updates from the work of doctoral student Mamadou Coulibaly, who focused on improving the nutrition, productivity, and health of livestock by increasing the diversity and biomass of shrubs and crops.

Collaborating farmers, including some IP members, provided testimonials on the use of woody fodder to combat gastrointestinal (GI) nematodes. The participants also discussed the positive impact of foliage-based rations on the growth performance of small ruminants, particularly praising the fodder and agronomic qualities of *Faidherbia albida*, which is being tested at the Katibougou station.

The common conclusions from the participants were:

- Incorporating dry leaves from trees and shrubs into the fattening rations of small ruminants promotes growth and helps reduce feed costs;

- The leaves and pods of *Faidherbia albida* provide high-quality feed for livestock;
- The presence of *Faidherbia albida* in a field improves soil fertility.

2.2.2 Workshop 2024 in Katibougou

The workshop aimed to share research findings on the use of local woody fodder species for sheep fattening and treating gastrointestinal (GI) parasites, as well as the prevalence of these parasites and the effectiveness of chemical dewormers in small ruminants.

Key messages shared during the workshop included:

- i) Collecting and drying fodder plant leaves in the shade at the end of the rainy season and using them in sheep's rations during the dry season reduces the need to purchase expensive concentrates;
- ii) Incorporating 30% of dry woody fodder plants such as *Pterocarpus santalinoides*, *Pterocarpus erinaceus*, and *Ficus sycomorus* into sheep's rations leads to significant weight gain;
- iii) Feeding fresh *Khaya senegalensis* leaves at the beginning and during the rainy season helps reduce intestinal parasites in sheep.

The participants confirmed the effectiveness of *Khaya senegalensis* leaves in controlling intestinal parasites in sheep and shared their knowledge that other species like *Entada africana* and *Anogeissus leiocarpus* (Ngalama) are also highly effective against gastrointestinal nematodes and certain diseases in donkeys.

In conclusion, producers were convinced that collecting and preserving leaves for use in dry-season feed rations significantly reduces the need for concentrated commercial feeds.

Moving forward, the next steps focused on promoting preventive health measures and the use of fresh *Khaya senegalensis* leaves in an anthelmintic treatment among relay producers and members of the IP.

At the various meetings, the following key messages were coined for dissemination:

- Woody plants provide sources of quality feed during the dry season, with their leaves and fruits offering critical nutrients (crude protein, minerals);
- Collecting, drying, and preserving the leaves of local and exotic woody forage species during times of abundance offers a valuable alternative feed resource in the lean period;
- Trees provide multiple benefits beyond animal nutrition and health, and all producers should preserve the valuable tree species in their fields;
- *Gliricidia sepium* contributes both to livestock feeding and soil fertility restoration;
- The efficient integration of agricultural, silvicultural and livestock activities, such as cropping, livestock farming, and tree management, promotes the sustainability of farming systems in the intervention zone;
- Incorporating leaves and pods of specific woody fodder plants helps enhance livestock performance and helps to reduce the incidence of certain parasitic diseases;
- Incorporating 30% of dry leaves (from either *Pterocarpus santalinoides*, *Pterocarpus erinaceus*, or *Ficus sycomorus*) into sheep's rations promotes weight gain and reduces feed costs;
- In mid-rainy season (July-August), infestation of small ruminants with gastrointestinal parasites is highest, and surveillance needs to be intensified at this moment;
- Fresh *Khaya senegalensis* leaves are an effective alternative to chemical dewormers in the control of intestinal parasites in sheep during the rainy season;

- Incorporating at least 40% of fresh *Khaya senegalensis* leaves into the daily ration of (housed) sheep for 14 days significantly reduces the fecal egg count in animals heavily infested with gastrointestinal helminths.

These messages will be communicated in leaflets and other dissemination materials, so as to spread the benefits of integrating woody plants into livestock management and highlight nature-based solutions for improving livestock health and productivity.

2.3 Senegal

In total the ISRA WP6 team held four meetings with farmers between 2022 and 2024, including one to present the rationing tool (with UNI KASSEL WP6 team), and the dissemination days held in Ouarkhokh.

- One meeting in Ouarkhokh, on 26 October 2022, specifically focused on WP6 activities. This involved exchanges with the managers and members of the Ouarkhokh IP to present the Excel® based tool OPÉRAS for calculating ruminant rations based on ligneous forage and to obtain feedback from producers on the utility of the tool and how to improve it (UNI KASSEL WP6);
- One meeting in Ouarkhokh on 23 June 2023 as a first dissemination day for specific WP6 results to train livestock producers;
- One meeting in Ouarkhokh on 30 October 2023 to present preliminary results of the activities of WPs 4, 6 and 7;
- One meeting in Ouarkhokh on 4 June 2024 for a presentation on the use of tree/shrub leaves as an alternative to costly chemical anthelmintics.

2.3.1 IP meeting in Ouarkhokh in 2022

During the first meeting, the UNI KASSEL WP6 team provided information on the components of the rationing tool OPÉRAS and explained its benefits for farmers who want to feed their ruminant animals (cattle, sheep, goats) in an adequate and cost-effective manner. Some platform members expressed interest in testing the tool. The participants agreed on the importance of this rationing tool, as it helps ensure a balance between the protein and energy requirements of animals and the protein and energy content of feed rations based on woody fodder, especially during the lean season.

2.3.2 Dissemination day I in Ouarkhokh in 2023

The WP6 team in Senegal used this opportunity to train producers on the use of the FAMACHA® card that helps to detect anaemia in small ruminants, which provides an indication of heavy infestation with specific intestinal helminths. Additionally, awareness was raised about the prevention of certain parasitic diseases caused by *Haemonchus contortus* (a blood-feeding intestinal nematode), which causes anaemia and oedema in sheep and goats and can lead to the animal's death. Participants listened attentively to the explanations and demonstration, and then practiced the use of the FAMACHA® card with an animal. They approved the usefulness of this method, which will enable them to alert veterinarians about sick animals and minimize the risk of mortality in small ruminants. In conclusion, the participants of the Ouarkhokh IP appreciated the very useful training provided by or team.

2.3.3 Dissemination day II in Ouarkhokh 2023

At the second dissemination day, the WP6 team conveyed key messages about the positive effect of woody fodder on sheep weight gain and its use as a feed supplement, which could significantly reduce the economic costs of livestock farming.

Several questions/remarks of stakeholders were noted, focusing on:

- The determination of the amount of fodder to give to the animals;
- Potential side effects from using woody forage in feed rations;
- Concerns about low weight gain;
- Various feeding practices tested at different times (morning, afternoon, and night);
- The possibility of using ligneous fodder as an alternative to expensive veterinary products for treating animals infested with parasites.

These concerns were addressed by the WP6 members in the feedback session. The importance of trees in maintaining soil fertility of cropland, feeding livestock, and benefiting the landscape in general was highlighted, emphasizing the need to raise farmers' awareness of sustainable tree management.

2.3.4 Dissemination day III in Ouarkhokh in 2024

The 2024 dissemination day in Ouarkhokh was used to present the results obtained within the SustainSahel project. During this meeting, the WP6 team conveyed the message that using tree and shrub leaves could serve as an alternative to costly chemical anthelmintics.

The practitioner participants responded to the input by stating:

- Ancestral practices of using woody plants to treat various animal ailments;
- The positive effects of fodder plants in combating intestinal parasites in animals;
- Innovative practices for ensuring the sustainability of forest resources;
- The need to consider alternatives for providing woody plant leaves in areas with few or no trees.

All participants together concluded that there is need for:

- Training and capacity building for farmers to ensure sustainable adoption of new practices in tree-based soil and animal management;
- Using various communication channels and creating simple, illustrated fact sheets to raise farmers' awareness about and adoption of good practices;
- Conducting further fattening and anthelmintic tests to confirm the results obtained to date.

As a next step, it was suggested that members of the Ouarkhokh IP could be involved in another on-farm feeding test aiming either at (i) sheep fattening or (ii) anthelmintic treatment.

The various discussions identified several key messages to be disseminated:

- The OPÉRAS rationing tool enables to identify rations with a good balance of protein and energy, prevents overfeeding, and promotes the sustainable use of fodder trees as animal feed;
- The FAMACHA® card helps identify and selectively treat the most anaemic animals, allowing for more efficient use of antiparasitic treatments in small ruminants;
- Incorporating *Balanites aegyptiaca* leaves and *Acacia tortilis* ssp. *raddiana* pods into sheep fattening rations increases the animals' daily weight gain;
- Fresh leaves of *Adansonia digitata*, *Ziziphus mauritiana* and *Balanites aegyptiaca* are effective alternatives to chemical anthelmintics (veterinary products) for controlling intestinal parasites in sheep during the rainy season;
- Incorporating more than 40% of fresh leaves of *Adansonia digitata*, *Ziziphus mauritiana*, *Khaya senegalensis* and *Balanites aegyptiaca* into the daily ration of (housed) sheep for 14 days significantly reduces the fecal egg count (that is, intestinal parasite load) during the rainy season.

3. Further dissemination activities

Beyond direct interaction with farmers during the above-described field days, workshops and IP meetings, dissemination activities of WP6 also include participation in international scientific meetings, the writing of scientific articles and information materials, testing and further development of the OPÉRAS rationing tool with the involvement of livestock keepers from all participating countries, and, together with AccessAgriculture, the production of a video on using tree leaves to control gastrointestinal nematodes in small ruminants. Additionally, the supervision of student trainees, whose dissertations or theses have been defended or are in progress, is also part of these efforts.

With regard to participation in international scientific meetings, WP6 PhD students attended the Tropentag conferences in 2022 and 2023, presenting posters and/or giving oral presentations. They also participated in international and regional symposia held in West Africa.

3.1 Tropentag 2022 Conference

Contributions from WP6 to Tropentag hybrid conference in Prague from 14-16 September 2022 were three online posters.

- Mamadou Coulibaly (IPR) "Perception of livestock keepers about woody fodder in the diet of sheep in two rural communes in Koulikoro region, Mali "
- Aminata Beye (ISRA): "Availability and use of woody fodder in the diet of small ruminants in the sylvo-pastoral zone of Senegal"
- Linda C.G. Traoré (INERA): "Farmers' appreciation of fodder trees and their preference by sheep in the Sudano-Sahelian zone of Burkina Faso"

3.2 International colloquium in Burkina Faso, 21-23 September 2022

The WP6 team from Burkina Faso took part in an international colloquium in Bobo Dioulasso (Burkina Faso) on the theme of "Biodiversity, ecosystems, climate change and exploitation of natural resources", with an oral presentation on "L'étude ethnobotanique de l'utilisation des plantes ligneuses fourragères par les populations de la commune de Guibaré dans la région du centre-nord du Burkina Faso". The paper was published in the International Journal of Biological and Chemical Sciences (Int. J. Biol. Chem. Sci. 17(1): 77-93).

3.3 Tropentag 2023 Conference

Contributions from the WP6 project during the Tropentag hybrid conference in Berlin from 20-22 September 2023 were two oral presentations as well as two poster presentations.

- Oral presentation by Mamadou Coulibaly (IPR) on "Efficacy of two anthelmintics against gastrointestinal nematodes of sheep in the silvopastoral zone of Senegal, Mali and Burkina Faso".
- Oral presentation by Sirki Fané (Uni KASSEL) on "Decomposition and nitrogen release patterns of shrubs/trees leafy biomass in the Sahelian zone of Senegal in West Africa".
- Poster presented by Linda C.G. Traoré (INERA) on "Prevalence and intensity of gastrointestinal nematode infection in small ruminants".
- Poster presented by Aminata Beye (ISRA) on "Use of trees and shrub by farmers to control gastrointestinal nematodes (GIN) in extensive livestock production systems of West Africa".

3.4. Malian Symposium of Applied Sciences, 28 July – 2 August 2024

Siriki Fané (Uni KASSEL) also took part in and presented an oral contribution on "Seasonal effects on the annual dynamics of litterfall and nutrient deposition by *Vitellaria paradoxa* C.F. Gaertner in agroforestry parks in southern Mali" at the Malian Symposium of Applied Sciences held in Bamako.

3.5 Tropentag 2024 Conference

Poster presented by Siriki Fané (Uni Kassel) on " Effects of plant leaves and their manure derivatives on *Sorghum bicolor* L. in the Sudano-Sahelian zone of Mali".

3.5 Publications and submissions

From WP6 members, in addition to the above-mentioned contribution to the International Journal of Biological and Chemical Sciences (Int. J. Biol. Chem. Sci. 17(1), 77-93), four manuscripts have been submitted to international peer reviewed journals, one of which has been published in the journal *Agroforestry Systems*.

- Mamadou Coulibaly, Drissa Coulibaly, Hawa Coulibaly, Regina Roessler, Baba Cissé, Eva Schlecht. Pastoral perceptions of fodder ligneous plants by herders in two rural communes of the Koulikoro region, Mali. International Journal of Biological and Chemical Sciences, submitted on 7 July 2024.
- Siriki Fané, Deogratias Kofi Agbotui, Sophie Graefe, L. Sanou, Sidi Sanogo, Andreas Buerkert (2024) Adoption of agroforestry systems by smallholders' farmers in the Sudano-Sahelian zones of Mali and Burkina Faso, West Africa. *Agroforestry Systems*, DOI: 10.1007/s10457-024-01020-8.
- Siriki Fané, Deogratias Kofi Agbotui, Sidi Sanogo, Andreas Buerkert. Community distance of agroforestry parklands affect tree diversity and carbon stocks in the Sudano-Sahelian zone of Mali. *Agriculture, Ecosystems and Environment*, submitted on 6 August 2024.
- Regina Roessler, Harun Cicek, Laurent Cournac, Moussa Gnissien, Julia Männle, Eric Koomson, Hassna Founoune-Mboup, Kalifa Coulibaly, Abdoul Aziz Diouf, Hadja Oumou Sanon, Georg Cadisch, Sophie Graefe. Towards transdisciplinary identification of suitable woody perennials for resilient agro-silvopastoral systems in the Sudano-Sahelian zone of West Africa. *Agroforestry Systems*, submitted on 8 April 2024.

3.6 Other dissemination activities and materials

The OPÉRAS rationing tool has been tested in the three participating countries, and the compilation of the results will allow for the tool's update and improvement until the end of the project in August 2025. A video on the use of tree leaves to control gastrointestinal nematodes in small ruminants has been produced with the support of AccessAgriculture and will be available online before the end of year 2024.

As part of the project's visibility efforts, the SustainSahel website was created at project start (<https://www.sustainsahel.net/index.html>). WP6 contributed to the site's updates by publishing news items, including:

- Modelling landscape-scale suitability of Crop-Shrub-Livestock systems: key insights and approaches (13 August 2024)
- Mulching - an ecological and economical technique in Senegal (10 July 2024)
- Sheep fattening based on woody fodder in rural areas (10 July 2024);
- The decomposition of plant leafy biomass and their manure derivatives in Koulikoro, Mali (30 December 2023)

- Annual litterfall of *Vitellaria paradoxa* Gaertn. C. F. in Mali (26 June 2023)
- Woody plants in the diet of small ruminants (13 February 2023)
- Introducing the updated feed ration calculator to innovation platforms - Field mission of University of Kassel (15 December 2022)
- Introducing a new staff member from University of Kassel (18 October 2022)
- Optimizing a feeding tool with nutritional details on shrub-foliage containing diets (4 July 2022)
- Fodder banks in Sub-Saharan Africa: A strategy for accelerating agroforestry innovations (28 April 2022)
- Introducing PhD student from ISRA in Senegal (11 March 2022)
- Introducing second PhD student from UNB in Burkina Faso (11 January 2022)
- Introducing second PhD student from IPR/IFRA in Mali (28 December 2021)
- Partner highlight: University of Kassel & PhD students (24 August 2021)

In addition to the PhD students, several DEA, BSc and MSc students were supervised by WP6 team members as part of the project's goal to enhance outreach also into the scientific community and train junior scientists. In total, 14 DEA, BSc, MSc and 4 PhD students were and are supervised. Of these students, six were female, representing 33%.

In Burkina Faso, eight students from various universities and professional schools were hired to complete their end-of-study diplomas on one of the WP6 themes. These students included six engineers and two technicians. To date, six students have successfully defended their dissertations.

At IPR in Mali, five students were supervised, including one master's student and one engineering student. In Senegal, one master's student was supervised as part of the project's activities.

Appendix I summarises the student reports and theses supported or currently in progress as part of the project.

4. Appendix

Appendix I

Table 1 Reports and theses supported or currently in progress as part of the SustainSahel project with information about the person's gender and type of the work

Name of student	Gender	Title of work	Type of work	University / School / Country	Date of submission / defence	Period and location of internship	WP6 Supervisor
BURKINA FASO							
TRAORE G. Linda	Female	Contribution of woody forage to improving livestock production in the northern Sudanian zone of Burkina Faso	Doctorate	Nazi Boni University - Rural Development Institute (UNB - IDR)	In progress	2021-2024, INERA/ Kamboinsé/Saria	H.O. SANON / E. SCHLECHT
OUATTARA Minata	Female	Contribution of fodder trees to ruminant livestock production in the Guibaré commune in Burkina Faso	Agricultural extension engineer	UNB - IDR	18/02/2022	January 2021 to October 2021, INERA/ Kamboinsé	L. TRAORE / H.O. SANON
OUEDRAOGO Denis	Male	Study of how people in the northern Sudanian zone of Burkina Faso carry out prophylaxis for small ruminants: the case of gastrointestinal parasitosis	Agricultural extension engineer	UNB - IDR	8/02/2023	06 September 2021 to 06 July 2022; INERA, Saria / Kamboinsé station	L. TRAORE / H.O. SANON
COMPAORÉ Sombéwindé Joseph Mukassa	Male	Characterisation of farmers' practices for harvesting and using the palatable biomass of four fodder ligneous plants in agroforestry parks in the northern Sudanian zone of Burkina Faso	Livestock engineer	UNB - IDR	7/02/2023	October 2021 to July 2022; INERA, Saria / Kamboinsé station	F. OBULBIGA / H.O. SANON
KONDOMBO Boureima	Male	Study of sheep feed preference for eight forage ligneous plants in the South Sudanian zone of Burkina Faso	Senior Livestock Technician	National School of Animal Husbandry and Health (ENESA)		June to September 2022; INERA, Saria / Kamboinsé station	L. TRAORE

Table 1 continued Reports and theses supported or currently in progress as part of the SustainSahel project with information about the person's gender and type of the work

Name of student	Gender	Title of work	Type of work	University School / Country	Date of submission / defence	Period location and of internship	WP6 Supervisor
KABORE Thérèse	Female	Seasonal variation in the prevalence and intensity of gastrointestinal strongyle infestation of small ruminants in the Boulkiemdé province of Burkina Faso	Engineer in environmental sciences and rural development; option: livestock farming	University of Dédougou (UDD)	September 2022	15 May 2022 to 15 March 2023; INERA, Saria / Kamboinsé station	L. TRAORE / H.O. SANON
GUIGUEMDE Michel	Male	Determining the best rates for incorporating woody fodder into animal feed	Livestock engineer	ENESA--	In progress	September 2023 to July 2024, INERA, Saria / Kamboinsé station	S. SANOU-SOME
TARPAGA F. Jean Eudes	Male	Optimisation of a pilot rationing tool OPÉRAS version 2.0	Degree in Animal Production	Saint Thomas Aquinas University	30/07/2024	June- December 2023, INERA, Saria/ Kamboinsé station	S. SANOU-SOME
NATADJA Silas	Male	Contribution of wood fodder to draught animal feeding	Livestock engineer	UNB - IDR	In progress	October 2023 to July 2024; INERA, Saria / Kamboinsé station	M. KABORE / H.O. SANON
MALI							
Mamadou COULIBALY	Male	Contribution des espèces ligneuses fourragères à l'amélioration de la production animale dans la zone soudano sahélienne du Mali	Doctorate	IPR/IFRA of Katibougou	In progress	2021-2024, Katibougou	D. COULIBALY / H. COULIBALY
Siriki FANE	Male	Adapted crop-shrub-livestock (CSL) systems and their contribution to soil fertility and sustainable cereal production of the Sudano-Sahelian zones in West Africa, Burkina Faso and Mali	Doctorate	UNI KASSEL	In progress	2021-2024, Kassel	A. BUERKERT

Table 1 continued Reports and theses supported or currently in progress as part of the SustainSahel project with information about the person's gender and type of the work

Name of student	Gender	Title of work	Type of work	University School / Country	Date of submission / defence	Period location and of internship	WP6 Supervisor
Youssouf COULIBALY	Male	Effect of rations incorporating fodder plants on the fattening performance of sheep at Maféya, Méguétan commune, Mali	Internship report	IPR/IFRA of Katibougou	November 2023	03 to 08/2023	D. COULIBALY
Baba CISSÉ	Male	Contribution to the identification of fodder plants for small ruminants in Mali	MSc dissertation	IPR/IFRA of Katibougou	March 2022	06/2021 to 01/2022, livestock sector of IPR/IFRA in Katibougou	D. COULIBALY / H. COULIBALY
Mariam BERTHE	Female	Effect of rations incorporating fodder plants on the fattening performance of sheep at Maféya, Meguetan commune, Mali	dissertation for end of engineering cycle	IPR/IFRA of Katibougou	December 2023	May to November 2023 at Maféya	D. COULIBALY / M. COULIBALY
Mamadou Sadio COULIBALY	Male	Study of the prevalence of gastrointestinal strongyles and coccidia of small ruminants in the communes of Doumba and Méguétan (Koulikoro Region)	Internship dissertation	IPR/IFRA of Katibougou	December 2022	May to November 2022	G. KEÏTA
Issa COULIBALY	Male	Study of the prevalence of small ruminant gastrointestinal strongyles in four villages in the commune of Méguétan	Internship dissertation	IPR/IFRA of Katibougou	October 2022	May to September 2022 at the IPR/IFRA in Katibougou	D. COULIBALY / H. COULIBALY

Table 1 continued Reports and theses supported or currently in progress as part of the SustainSahel project with information about the person's gender and type of the work

Name of student	Gender	Title of work	Type of work	University / School / Country	Date of submission / defence	Period location and of internship	WP6 Supervisor
SENEGAL							
Aminata BEYE	Female	Design of integrated and sustainable systems (crops, shrubs and animals) favourable to the mitigation of greenhouse gas emissions in the sylvo-pastoral zone of Senegal	Doctorate	Cheikh Anta Diop University (UCAD)/Senegal	in progress	2021-2024 at ISRA/ Ouarkhokh	T. MBAYE / E. SCHLECHT / M. F. BA
Soda NDONGO	Female	Effect of supplementing sheep fattening rations with <i>Balanites aegyptiaca</i> (L.) Del. leaves and <i>Acacia tortilis</i> ssp <i>raddiana</i> (Savi) fruits on the technical and economic performance of sheep in the sylvopastoral zone of Senegal	Master 2 dissertation (MSc thesis)	University Gaston Berger - UGB; UFR of Agronomic Sciences, Aquaculture and Food Technologies	end of November 024	June 2023- November 2023 at the CNRF	T. MBAYE / M. F. BA / A. BEYE